

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING FOLKLORE SONGS IN EDUCATION

Allayarova N.N.

Urganch State Pedagogical Institute

Senior teacher of the Department of Music Education

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Abstract: In this article, the use of folk songs and their performance methods in continuing education, national music, children's folk songs, in music culture lessons held in general secondary schools and through these songs, young people are taught about their motherland, increasing the love for uni songs and its analysis.

Key words: Educational melody, song, performance folk art, children's folklore songs, performance, local style, musical analysis, national music.

Introduction.

It is one of the important tasks facing our country to educate the students who are the creators of our future through the art of music, to become spiritually mature, intellectually mature, physically healthy people who have a conscious attitude to the values of national culture. After all, making a person interested in music from childhood, developing musical perception and imagination is extremely necessary for every society. In this process, music reminds a person of his humanity, instills hope and confidence in the future in his heart.

In this regard, the President *Sh.M. Mirziyoev* emphasizes the following: "*The art of music as a cultural phenomenon has unlimited opportunities to educate and mature the new generation. Young people who are familiar with art have a higher attitude towards life, respect for national customs and universal values. In this sense, if we say that music has a divine influence that cannot be measured with anything, we will be saying the same truth.*" Therefore, it is necessary to develop students' musical level, increase their love and enthusiasm for the art of music. Our state is paying special attention to the development of the range of knowledge and practical skills, especially to improving the professional skills of students who have a talent for music, and creating the necessary conditions. The song plays a very important role. Because the song contains harmonious images of artistic and musical ideas. In this regard, the meaningfulness of national and folk songs is special. The national culture, emotional experiences, human qualities, and spiritual world of our people are reflected in national songs¹. Today, large-scale works are being carried out in our country during the new stage of our national development.

The rapid development of science and technology in the world, the introduction of innovative technologies into life at a rapid pace increases the demand for educational processes, including pedagogical technologization of music education processes, improvement of new conditions of music education. we have the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "*On approval of the concept of development of the public*

¹ Allayarova, N. (2023). Characteristics Of Using Music In Physical Exercises. *Development and innovations in science*, 2(2), 71-73.

education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PF-5712, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2019 *"On measures to further develop the art of charity"* PQ-4320, September 5, 2018 *"On additional measures to improve the management system of public education"* PF- Decree No. 5538 of the Cabinet of Ministers of May 18, 2018 *"On the organization and holding of the Great Silk Road International Music Festival"* Decision No. 371 of the Cabinet of Ministers of June 27, 2018 *"On the organization of the Festival of Lights and International Folklore"* This research serves to a certain extent the implementation of the tasks specified in the implementation and transfer and other regulatory legal documents related to this activity.

The song form of music is the main educational material of the lesson. It differs from the melody in that, as a result of combining the artistic word for the song and the melody, an artistic idea is created from the generalization of the verse and melody. Therefore, as a result of understanding the musical tone and artistic meaning of the song, the student creates an artistic idea. Harmonization of music education with national heritage, national traditions and customs, preservation and enrichment of national cultural examples, recognition of education as a very important factor of national development, history and culture of other nations the implementation of a new education system focused on respect made it possible to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process.

In the treasury of the Uzbek folk music heritage, children's folk music works and children's songs, which combine the spiritual world of adults and young children, have an important place. Such songs are distinguished by their unique expression of children's life, psyche, various children's games, sayings, animals and plants, and the nature of natural phenomena. Children's songs, like popular types of folk music, have an artistic and ideological content, the text is simple, extremely concise, playful and dance-like in nature. The content of music education in educational institutions at all stages of the continuous education system was radically updated and enriched with information about the national musical heritage. As a result, the growing young generation had the opportunity to become familiar with the history of national music, its development, unique trends and traditions, as well as the creative work of artists who made a great contribution to the development of national music art. .

Debate:

Uzbek national music art has the ability to fully reflect the spirit of the people, to express its unique lifestyle, life goals - aspirations, thoughts and mental state, and organizes social education. is considered one of the effective means of Vocational college students will get the following information and knowledge while listening to samples of musical works on *"Spiritual Days"* .:

- *They will learn about the authors of musical works of national and classic folklore songs, their lives and works.*
- *They will be aware of the differences of Uzbek national musical works from the music of other nations.*
- *While enjoying the skills of the performers, they can evaluate the specific features of the performance style, the achievements and shortcomings of the performer.*
- *They will be able to perform samples of Uzbek classical musical works and provide information about them to the individual in the future.*

In the primary classes of general education schools, the teaching of children's folk songs, tunes and simple sayings, which are mainly characteristic of children's thinking and more

related to games, plays an important role in the formation of the national basis of music education². Therefore, the appropriate use of children's folklore songs from the national musical heritage of our people in music lessons, their implementation, taking into account the styles of their performance, requires a unique pedagogical approach, knowledge and skill from each music teacher. Especially in them, through music, the opportunity to educate qualities such as national character, awareness of the national minority will expand. In this case, it is necessary to achieve that a positive attitude towards folk music is formed, clear ideas about the listened work are formed, and they are able to appreciate it. A student who has formed a positive attitude towards folk music will broadly express his ideas about the listened piece, and certain evaluation criteria may appear in it. Because a positive attitude is manifested as motives of active perception.

Result.

We know that the Republic of Uzbekistan is divided into five local styles: Bukhara-Samarkand, Kashkadarya-Surkhandarya, Fergana-Tashkent, Khorezm and Karakalpak styles. These oases differ from each other in their customs, traditions, wedding ceremonies, songs and performance styles. Acquainting children with national folk music and folkloric samples in a high-quality education to meet the necessary needs of music teachers first of all requires dedication to their profession, deep love for folk music and high level of professional skills. Effective application of children's folklore songs to the teaching process requires positive solving of a number of tasks.

Conclusion

So, to create a pedagogical and methodical system of musical culture, spiritual and artistic aesthetic education of students through children's folklore songs, to study the existing experiences accumulated until today, to study the activities of folklore-ethnographic ensembles operating in different regions. It is possible to strengthen the national foundations of musical education by collecting, summarizing and applying to the educational process examples of national classic songs, folklore, children's folklore in their repertoire.

Folk songs have been connecting hearts for centuries with the subtlety of expression and the strength of the image of the mental state. The level of their artistic image increases over the years. It can be seen that the rituals of educational and educational importance, as well as the sayings that are performed to them, value each passing day of the population, enrich the passing life with meaning, and leave it to the future generation, proving their loyalty to the values that have become a tradition.

² Kh, I. T. (2021). Characteristics of khorezm doston art. *Экономика и социум*, (3-1 (82)), 96-98.

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